

COLOR PAINTING AND PENCIL IN FIGURATIVE ART THE ROLE OF THE IMAGE

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Annotation. A detailed description of the role of painting and pencil in fine art is given in this article. The means of expression of painting, the effect of colors on the human psyche and the aesthetic value are emphasized. The role of the pencil image in the reflection of accuracy, detail and movement is illuminated. Both types of art have their own characteristics and significance, providing artists with a wide range of opportunities. This article reveals their place and importance in the fine arts through a comparison of painting and pencil image.

Key words; in fine arts, painting, graphics-pencil, sculpture, aesthetic assessment, portraits, landscapes, still life;

As you know, in the process of the historical development of art, its types also began to form. Graphics, painting, sculpture, architecture, folk applied decorative art, etc. All of them are an important part of human and spiritual life, expressing high artistic ideas, concepts about beauty. One art form differs from another in its content, artistic-expressive means and style, influence on feelings and vital importance.

Graphics-pencil is a type of fine art that includes both image and printed art. It also has its own pictorial, expressive means and the possibility of impressiveness. "Graphics" is of great importance due to the sharp development of the method of printing art polygraph and collegraphically precise contrast linear pencil and for the most convenience in terms of phototechnical production in the printing of magazines and books.

In graphic art, the pilgrimage of the image is achieved by the fact that artistic means are assembled and focused on one point, therefore, in addition to works completed in graphics, drafts from nature are also independently worked out sketches of paintings, sculptures and architectural works, which also have independent artistic value. By the technician, graphics are divided into picture and print graphics. Graphics are the most ancient and traditional type of art-the origin of painting, external drawings, drawings on antique dishes, and the basis of the image is Lines, color spots. In terms of its constructive-pictorial and artistic possibilities of influence, Infinity in its styles and large-scale, the artist's creative path in painting graphics is a constant dialogue with nature.

In painting with painting, there are many commonalities, the border between which is conditional. According to its function, the workshop, book, newspaper and magazine, folk practical graphics and poster are different from each other.

Early graphics were mostly common in the Renaissance drum. It also addresses traditional fine arts genres. The first art of printed graphics is the book, The main area of which is applied to the decoration of interiors due to its multi-circulation release, reaching the public, as well as the quality of decoration. Painting is an art form in which an image or cardboard is created through colors on a solid surface of the fabric. Means such as light - shade, applied color impressiveness factor and composition, Colorite provide the opportunity to create the size, shape, originality, width, depth and light air environment of objects. Painting gives a state of stagnant and temporary development a state of calmness and emotional mental fullness, a tassurat of movement. This condition allows you not only to clearly see the level of vision of being by eye, but also to express a wide picture of life. Also in the color image, the essence of historical processes is revealed, the inner experiences of a person are expressed.

The Role Of Painting In Fine Art

Painting is one of the main areas of Fine Art, in which images are created through different combinations of colors. The main purpose of painting is to express feelings, mood, and various states using colors. Using the painting method, artists create a variety of subjects, including portraits, landscapes, still lifes and many other genres.

The art of painting has existed in the history of mankind since ancient times, it has been developing with its means and techniques of expression. Examples of medieval miniature art, Renaissance frescoes, impressionists, and modern abstract art, for example, reflect the various stages of painting.

The Importance Of Painting

1. Aesthetic assessment: painting creates aesthetic beauty that is perceived through the human eye and through it affects the human psyche.
2. Means of expression: with the help of Colors, the artist manifests his feelings, thoughts and views.
3. Strong effect: due to the psychological effects of colors, they can evoke certain emotions, raise or calm the mood.

The Position Of The Pencil Image

A pencil image (graph) is a drawing using a pencil on a paper or other level. This method uses pencils, colored pencils, charcoal, and other graphics tools. The pencil image is represented by more lines, shading and punctuation, in contrast to the painting.

The peculiarity of the pencil image is that it requires clarity and tenderness. The pictures created using a pencil can be very clear and detailed. This method is often used when creating portraits, illustrations, and sketches.

The Importance Of Pencil Image

- ✓ Detailing: Pencil image is convenient for the reflection of very delicate details.

- ✓ Movement and dynamics: with the help of lines and shadows, it is easier to create movement and dynamics in the image.
- ✓ Easy implementation: you don't need a lot of equipment to create an image using pencil and paper, which makes it popular.

In the image, the pencil must be perfect, otherwise different paints will also simply not perfectly represent the construction, volume of the thing and the item. Even colored greases given to the fabric, which represent a subtle change in colors depending on the perspective of the air, cannot show spatial width on their own. Only the pencil, which is depicted correctly following the rules of perspective, makes the colors look even more attractive.

If the landscape of nature is depicted without the observance of the laws of perspective, the role of the color that represents latitude is irrelevant. Painters define painting as "one hundred percent pencil and one hundred percent painting".

In painting, it is necessary that the colors are inextricably linked with the pencil. That is, to start the work in color, it is darcor to describe the size of the shape by means of colors, having marked the necessary places of Natura in the pencil and forgetting the conditional lines of the shape.

D.N.In kardovsky's opinion, if we say that painting is the continuation of a pencil in color, the interpretation of the form in color begins with a pencil, and in the process of creation it is corrected several times, polished with colors. A thorough mastery of pencil skills is a guarantee of creating unique works of painting. P.P.Konchalovsky, seeing the essence of pencil painting in painting, wrote: "the real method of painting is painting, which is given by absolutely accurate delivery of the form."

In conclusion, it can be said that in fine art, both painting and pencil occupy an important place in the image. While painting is more the power of colors and the means of expression, the pencil image is effective in reflecting precision, detail

and movement. Both methods provide art lovers with ample opportunities to express their creative ideas and feelings.

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